

Beyond Prediction Accuracy: A Decision-Aware Framework for Demand Forecasting in Small Business Environments

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Abstract

Demand Forecasting based on uncertainties makes anticipating outcomes during supply chain management and operational planning one of the most critical tasks for a small business enterprise. Hence, most data-driven business intelligence models are primarily focused on the accuracy of predictive systems. Therefore, little attention has been paid to how these predictive forecasting systems translate into the accuracy of operational decisions in business environments. This study proposes a data-driven decision support system, which is examined on a large database, that can merge time-constrained forecasting with a rule-based decision-aware layer to evaluate both predictive performance and operational decision quality.

The proposed system employed the Random Forest Regression model as its chosen method to train data. Selected for its interpretability, random forest regression uses daily, weekly, and monthly demand for products in the chosen sales data to predict future actions. Before the use of the training method, the dataset employed is first preprocessed so that it features temporal and lag-based variables. Then the sales data, empowered by the new features, was trained to demand forecast. Later, a decision support layer made of dynamically designed thresholds is used to transfer the decision forecasts into actionable, supported, business-ready decisions.

The developed framework was evaluated using the traditional predictive metrics and business-level decision metrics. The results achieved by the predictive metric, assessed by calculating a Mean Absolute error (MAE), were approximately 423 units, and the results produced by the decision metric, evaluated by calculating the alignment between recommended actions and actual demand outcomes, was 70%. This outcome indicated that predictive outcomes do not necessarily improve operational decisions. It was realized that improvements in predictive performance do not necessarily translate into improved operational decisions.

This research highlights the importance of an accessible, supporting decision-aware evaluation framework that connects analytical decision forecasts to practical decisions. Also, it contributes to small business settings and analytical environments by providing an interpretable decision-support mechanisms that bridge between predictive analytics and practical business decision-making in resource-constrained environments.

Keywords: Decision Intelligence, Predictive Analytics, demand forecasting, decision support systems, machine learning, business analytics

I. Introduction

Reliable demand forecasting becomes a pivotal input for effective planning and decision-making in any small organization [1]. Many small establishments face one main problem when they are looking to use business intelligence to analyze their future product demand. One of their main issues is accessing a reliable decision forecasting system to support them with an accurate estimation of future demands. The issue for most small enterprises is to allocate the right quantity of products to sell. If the wrong amount of items were to be ordered, they either incur extra costs or lose profit when it occurs [2]. Thus, for small operations which normally have access to limited operational resources [2], Having a system that not only helps with forecasting decisions but also sending those decisions through a data-driven support system to indicate the most operational verdict is crucial.

The importance of managing the performance of logistics and supply chain has led to significant advancement in the field of business intelligence [3]. Decision forecasting studies based on the historical data available have formed the heart of many studies in recent years. Several different systems were used while approaching these research. Training techniques like regression methods and ensemble learning, and providing a deep learning structure were among them [3]. This study approaches the Random Forest Regression method that is popular for its strength, ease of interpretation, and the capacity to model nonlinear relationships based on business data structures [4].

The majority of the researches mainly focus on forecasting data through the prediction of error metrics [5] such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), or Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) [3]. It has been observed that they are important factors to calculate statistic accuracy of the results; however on their own, they are unable to provide sufficient evidence to indicate whether these analytical answers can provide the highest performance operational decision in actual business settings [6].

Managing Business and supply chain demands is at the core of modern businesses. Business values might be hurt if they are only based on using ideal analytical decision forecasts. Overestimation and underestimation of a system that has only been trained analytically may cause significant damage to small businesses with limited resources [2]. There is a gap between decision forecasts and sensible operational decisions that are mostly ignored [6]. This gap has a significant effect on managing small business enterprise decisions for the future.

This study suggests the addition of a decision support system that can connect time constrained forecasting with a data-based decision support layer to link the decision forecast with an evaluated decision support framework. To overcome the limitations of a statistical decision forecast, this framework uses the history of previous sales data to transfer the business intelligence predictions into a rule-based system [7]. Moreover, beside building a decision support mechanism, this system provides a base to compare predicted results with real world business outcomes. This paper tries to significantly contribute to bridging the gap between

acceptable business predictive intelligence forecasts and effectively operable business results [6].

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. The methodology, including the introduction to our dataset preprocessing, added features, and the use of random forest regression, is presented in the Methodology Section. In the Results section, we discuss the decision support layer, calculating Mean Absolute Error, and decision accuracy, and we discuss whether prediction is enough for a quality decision and results. The future work section contains conclusions and future work suggestions.

II. Related Work

Reliable demand forecasting becomes a pivotal input for effective planning and decision making in any small organization [3]. Many small organizations face reliability and sometimes interpretability problems when they are looking to use business intelligence to analyze their future supply management. Recent studies show that machine learning models can improve forecasting performance by capturing nonlinear patterns in historical sales data [5]. Among these studies, some researches use methods Like Random Forest Regression method [4] which is popular for its strength, ease of interpretation, and the capacity to model nonlinear relationships based on business data structures [3].

In addition, decision support systems have increasingly incorporated predictive analytics [7] to support inventory and operational planning [2]. Recent research in prescriptive analytics suggests that the business value of predictive models depends not only on forecast accuracy but also on the quality of the decisions generated from those forecasts [6].

Despite these advancements, the majority of the projects mainly focus on forecasting data through the prediction of error metrics [1] such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), or Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), with little to no attention to the gap between decision forecasts and sensible operational decisions [6]. This study addresses this gap and studies the addition of a decision support system that can connect operational forecasting with a data-based decision support layer to connect the decision forecast with an evaluated decision support framework.

III. Methodology

A. Research Design

This paper proposes a data-driven decision support system for demand forecasting in small business environments. The system employs a combination of data preprocessing, feature engineering, a decision modeling layer, and rule generation into a system that provides

operational business decisions. The proposed applied business intelligence system helps to evaluate the quality of decisions and the need for an accurate decision support system.

B. Dataset

The data used in this project is the *Store Sales-Time series Forecasting* from Kaggle. This dataset is a publicly available retail dataset including time stamped historical sales records, product information, and temporal variables. This research targeted daily sales data that is time stamped and sorted to train a prediction forecast model for decision forecasting future product demands. For ease of interpretability in small business enterprises, the training method used in this paper simplified the dataset to one store, which is more relevant to such businesses.

C. Data Preprocessing

Before the use of the training method, the dataset employed is first preprocessed. In this procedure, data is parsed based on daily timestamps. Then, to make a more versatile dataset, weekly and monthly time stamps have been added to make both short-term and long-term training possible. Afterwards, data is sorted by daily calendar-based date stamps. Data that contained missing values was then filtered out to reduce the chance of facing errors or crashing in the training system.

Component	Configuration
Dataset	Store Sales – Time Series Forecasting
Business Scope	Single-store environment
Product Family	GROCERY I
Forecasting Type	Time-series demand forecasting
Temporal Features	Day, Month, Weekday
Lag Features	lag_7, lag_14, lag_30
Forecasting Model	Random Forest Regression
Number of Trees	200
Maximum Depth	10
Evaluation Metric	Mean Absolute Error
Decision Thresholds	33rd percentile / 66th percentile

D. Feature Engineering

To improve the dataset to become more accurately dependable, in the next step, temporal and lag-based variables were added. Firstly, to add temporal data, the data turn into day, week, and day of week analytic variables. Then the data empowered by adding Lag_7 and Lag_14 rows

to the dataset to separate short-term trends from long-term behaviors. Afterwards, we cleaned the dataset one more time, and it was now ready for a training system.

E. Forecasting model

This paper chose Random Forest regression as the training method for the chosen database. For training an accurate business intelligence system, a robust, dynamic, and nonlinear system must be available, and Random Forest Regression is a candidate that can provide all these objectives. Random Forest is an ensemble of several decision trees. The sheer number of trees makes it ideal to train regression tasks. Sales data are usually dynamic, and the variety of different decision trees makes this system perfectly versatile for processing dynamic and noisy data [4]. The ensemble of several trees that are each individually trained makes little room for mistakes, which makes this system robust and reliable. Individual trees may be weak, but together they become accurate and trustworthy. In this random forest model, the number of trees is set to 200, which is big enough for small business datasets but good enough to avoid overfitting. Max_depth is also set to 10 to control model complexity and avoid overfitting.

Random forest is computationally less expensive compared to other deep learning models, therefore it's perfect for small business settings [3]. Also, because of the several trained trees available. It is ideal to process different variables. Also, the combination of the results from each different tree makes this system more robust and less prone to noise and mistakes.

F. Decision Support Layer

The presented forest tree forecasting model analyzes the data through the evaluation of Mean Absolute Error (MAE) [1]. MAE is calculating the average size of mistakes in the results of the random forest prediction. Mean Absolute Error is calculated by the formula below.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|$$

It is the sum of the absolute value of each prediction divided by the total number of observations. To support these calculations and to achieve a more reliable operational forecast, this research also added a supporting layer. The combination of these two systems makes an ensemble learning system. Research shows that ensemble learning results in even more accurate forecasts. This decision supporting layer directs the results to a decision support layer made of dynamically designed thresholds, which is used to transfer the decision forecasts into actionable supported business-ready decisions [5]. In this research, it was interpreted that each product a business provides is either selling well, not well, or as usual, therefore creating a simple and understandable decision-support system suitable for small enterprises, demand levels are divided into three levels, which made 33% and 66% thresholds. The algorithm is designed based on these actual data thresholds. If data reached under 33%, it indicates low demand; therefore, reducing stock is the best action as a result, and if the demand of a product is between the two thresholds it has its usual demand; therefore, the stock must be maintained, and if the product reaches over 66% threshold in sales, the stock of this item needs to be increased. This decision support system is used because it's easy to interpret and use in small business enterprises that do not have access to large datasets and complex systems [6]. It is also

scalable and adaptable across different products that the businesses might add in the future. This support system makes results easy to understand, which is most important in small business environments [2]. This factor on its own, makes results understandable and trustworthy for decision makers who are looking to make operational decisions in environments where sources are limited, and confusion might come at a cost.

G. Performance Evaluation

To evaluate the performance of the proposed system, two different performances must be calculated: predictive performance and operational performance.

Predictive performance was analyzed using Mean Absolute Error (MAE). MAE is perfectly suited for this calculation because it provides an interpretable error measure based on the provided sales dataset scale.

Operational performance calculated by evaluating decision accuracy. Decision accuracy is measured by analyzing the difference between the actual results and the predicted results.

Using the calculated result of both metrics allowed this study to evaluate not only statistical forecasting performance but also the evaluation of a supporting operational performance.

IV. Results and Discussion

A. Forecasting Performance

In this research, the Random Forest Regression model was applied to a database of sales that is characteristically noisy and fluctuating. Therefore, when the dataset trained and the predictions made, it is time to evaluate the prediction performance. This purpose was achieved by calculating MAE, which indicates on average how far off the predictions of this system are from actual demands [3]. In this project, the MAE achieved is rounded up to 423.43. Considering the value of predictions and the average of the daily sales, which is 2635, and the maximum number of sales at 5386, this result shows that even though the data was noisy, the system designed was stable enough to make predictions with reasonable results.

B. Decision Performance

The result achieved from the first layer is not robust enough on its own to lead to operational actions, hence a decision support layer was added to achieve better predictions. The support layer is later applied to the system. The outcome of this independent application was almost 70% decision accuracy. Decision accuracy is calculated as follows

$$Decision Accuracy = \frac{\text{Number of Correct Decisions}}{\text{Total Number of Decisions}}$$

This result shows that 7 out of 10 recommendations this system made matched the desired observed demand category. Comparing predicted action vs action derived from observed sales category suggested that the outcome of inventory actions is aligned with real-world demands.

C. Comparative Interpretation

The results indicated that improving prediction accuracy on its own does not necessarily lead to better decision performance.

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error	423.48
Decision Accuracy	70%

For instance, in this research, the thresholds were designed as follows

Demand Category	Threshold Range	Recommended Action
Low Demand (<120)	Below 33rd percentile	Reduce Stock
Medium Demand	Between 33rd and 66th percentile	Maintain Stock
High Demand (>4000)	Above 66th percentile	Increase Stock

Now, when the predicted data showed 2800, even though the real desired data was 2600, the system still resulted in deciding on the right action, which in this case was increasing stock.

This result leads to show the necessity for the availability of a decision-aware evaluation system [6].

V. Future work

A. Summary

This paper proposes a data-driven decision support system for demand forecasting in small business environments. The approach combined a Random Forest predictive model [4] with a rule-based decision layer that converts forecasts into actionable inventory decisions [6]. Decision thresholds are dynamically derived from historical demand distributions, enabling adaptive and interpretable recommendations.

The forecasted results from this system are examined through both traditional predictive metrics and business level decision metrics, assessed by calculating a Mean Absolute error and calculating the alignment between recommended actions and actual demand outcomes. The calculated results from the predictive layer and operational layer suggested that predictive

outcomes do not necessarily improve operational decisions. It also proves the need for decision-aware evaluation in machine learning systems.

The Predictive layer resulted in calculating a Mean Absolute error, that observed in this set of data is 423.75. While the operational layer was evaluated by calculating the alignment between recommended actions and actual demand outcomes resulted in 70% accuracy. This outcome suggested that predictive outcomes do not necessarily improve operational decisions. It also demonstrates the need for decision-aware evaluation in machine learning systems [6].

This research studied the importance of an accessible supporting framework that connects analytical decision forecasts to practical decisions. Also, it contributes to small business settings and systematic environments by making a support system that bridges interpretability and practical decision values.

B. Limitations

This research tried to introduce the positive impacts of a data driven decision support system in small business environments. Therefore, it is still in its early stages. There are limitations that apply to this study that can later be removed to expand the impact of this research. The limitations applied are using data from only one store and one category of products, not including holidays and promotions and skipping economic indicators. Future studies may demonstrate that the proposed system can be implemented in multi-location and multi-category businesses as well.

C. Future Work

This research has many potentials. There are several challenges yet to be addressed. The results can be improved by using gradient boosting [8] or other hybrid models. Cost-sensitive decisions and profit optimization can be added to expand this research. Also, the system can be sent through reinforcement learning [9] [10].

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